

NOTES

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkaline Earth Metals. Part-IV. Magnesium(II) and Calcium(II) Complexes with 1,3-Diphenylpropane-1,3-dione and Salicylaldehyde, 2-Hydroxyacetophenone, Pentane-2,4-dione or 1-Phenylbutane-1,3-dione

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WE have already reported¹ the mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals of the type MLL' . The present paper describes the mixed ligand complexes of the type $MLL'(H_2O)_2$, where $M = Mg^{II}$ and Ca^{II} ; $HL' = 1,3$ -diphenylpropane-1,3-dione; and $HL'' =$ salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, pentane-2,4-dione or 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde (E. Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (John Baker), pentane-2,4-dione (I.D.P.L.) and ethanol were purified by distillation, and 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (Fluka) and 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (SD's) were recrystallised from ethanol before use. $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ were of A.R. grade.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes: To ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (about 8 mmol in

20 cm³), ethanolic solutions (~20 cm³) of the two different carbonyl compounds (1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione and salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, pentane-2,4-dione or 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione) were added in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio. The pH of the resulting clear solution was raised to ~8.5 by adding aqueous ammonia (1 part ammonia of sp. gr. 0.888 and 3 parts water) dropwise with stirring. After 0.5 h, the resulting yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The mixed ligand complexes are stable solids, insoluble in water, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride and soluble in DMSO. The complexes of calcium are soluble in methanol, whereas those of magnesium are insoluble except that of salicylaldehyde and 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione which are soluble. Metal ion appears to be hexacoordinated in these complexes and the probable geometry may be octahedral.

Thermogravimetric analysis: Thermogravimetric data confirm the presence of two coordinated water molecules in the mixed ligand complexes. After the loss of two water molecules at 220–240°, the complex $Mg(bzac)(dbzm)(H_2O)_2$ exhibits constant weight for a while, then a continuous loss in weight and finally the complex is converted to MgO at ~950°. Similarly, in case of the complex $Ca(hap)(dbzm)(H_2O)_2$, the weight remains constant after the loss of two water molecules at ~180°, then a continuous loss in weight and finally the complex is

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Mg^{II} AND Ca^{II}

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Colour, nature	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				O	H	M
1.	$Mg(H_2O)_2(sal)(dbzm)$	Yellow solid	135	63.84 (65.28)	4.87 (4.98)	6.01 (6.00)
2.	$Mg(H_2O)_2(hap)(dbzm)$	Light yellow solid	145	63.18 (65.97)	5.41 (5.29)	5.71 (5.80)
3.	$Mg(H_2O)_2(acac)(dbzm)$	Light yellow solid	165	61.70 (62.76)	5.48 (5.79)	6.27 (6.35)
4.	$Mg(H_2O)_2(bzac)(dbzm)$	Light yellow solid	158	66.28 (67.50)	5.86 (5.48)	5.38 (5.46)
5.	$Ca(H_2O)_2(sal)(dbzm)$	Yellow solid	238	62.80 (62.84)	4.90 (4.79)	9.58 (9.53)
6.	$Ca(H_2O)_2(hap)(dbzm)$	Light yellow solid	239	61.90 (63.57)	5.14 (5.10)	9.24 (9.22)
7.	$Ca(H_2O)_2(acac)(dbzm)$	Light yellow solid	235	58.95 (59.05)	5.72 (5.73)	10.86 (10.87)
8.	$Ca(H_2O)_2(bzac)(dbzm)$	Light yellow solid	86	64.20 (64.26)	5.40 (5.39)	8.90 (8.99)

*sal = salicylaldehyde, hap = 2-hydroxyacetophenone, acac = acetylacetone (pentane-2,4-dione), bzac = benzoylacetone (1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione), dbzm = dibenzoylmethane (1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione).

converted to CaO at $\sim 850^\circ$. The complex $\text{Ca}(\text{acac})\text{-(dbzm)}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ loses the two water molecules at $\sim 200^\circ$ and is finally converted to CaO at $\sim 850^\circ$. In case of the complex $\text{Ca}(\text{bzac})\text{-(dbzm)}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, the two water molecules appear to be weakly coordinated since these are lost at significantly lower temperature, just beyond 100° . After that the weight of the compound remains constant upto $\sim 200^\circ$ and then there is a gradual loss in weight and finally the complex gets converted to CaO at $\sim 950^\circ$.

Infrared spectra: The concerned ir absorption bands of mixed ligand complexes of Mg^{II} and Ca^{II} along with their assignments are recorded in Table 1. Appearance of strong absorption band at $\sim 1600\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of coordinated C=O groups. In free salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone bands at 1660 cm^{-1} and 1650 cm^{-1} respectively have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$. Bellamy and Beecher³ reported $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band at 1724 cm^{-1} in acetylacetone and benzoylacetone. The lowering of the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ in the mixed ligand complexes supports the coordination of the C=O groups to the metal atom. Bands at $420\text{--}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are absent in the free ligands may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ of M-O-C bonds. Weak bands at $220\text{--}300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ stretching of M-O-H bonds formed by the coordination of water molecule to the metal atom.

Nmr spectrum: ^1H nmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6 ; 90 MHz) of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOCH}_2]_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOCH}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Mg}$ reveals complex multiplet at $\delta 7\text{--}8$ (ArH). In free benzoylacetone, the resonances due to the CH_2 and CH protons have been reported at $\delta 2.19$ and 6.18 respectively⁴, which are found shifted upfield ($\delta 1.66$ and 5.66) in this complex. In free dibenzolymethane, the signal due to the CH proton appears at $\delta 6.82$ which also shifted upfield ($\delta 6.40$ ppm) in the mixed ligand complex. Upfield shifts of these protons confirm the coordination of the C=O groups to the magnesium atom.

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Some Phenoxides and Mixed Phenoxy Derivatives of Antimony(III) : $[\text{SbCl}_{3-n}(\text{OAr})_n]$

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COMPARED to simple alkoxides, phenoxides of antimony(III) have received less attention^{1,2}. Although only some simple phenoxides of antimony(III) have been reported in the literature^{1,2}, yet little is known about the corresponding derivatives of sterically crowded aryloxy ligands. In the present communication we report the results on the synthesis and properties of some sterically crowded phenoxides and some mixed chlorophenoxide derivatives of antimony(III), $[\text{SbCl}_{3-n}(\text{OAr})_n]$.

Experimental

Antimony(III) chloride and phenols were distilled before use. All manipulations were carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions using dry solvents. Molecular weights of the derivatives were determined in benzene using a Gallenkamp ebulliometer. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3 or CCl_4) on a JEOL FX 90 Q using TMS as external indicator.

Synthesis of $[\text{SbCl}_2(\text{OAr})]$: Freshly distilled antimony(III) chloride (3.24 g, 1.42 mmol) and 2,4,6-trimethylphenol (1.99 g, 1.46 mmol) were dissolved together in benzene (~ 80 ml). The contents were refluxed till the evolution of HCl gas ceased. The excess of solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to yield light pink crystals in quantitative yield (97%). The product was further purified by recrystallisation in n-hexane (Table 1).

Synthesis of $[\text{SbCl}(\text{OAr})_2]$: Potassium (1.07 g, 27.43 mmol) and 2,4,6-trimethylphenol (3.67 g, 26.98 mmol) were refluxed together (~ 3 h) in tetrahydrofuran (~ 20 ml) till a clear solution was obtained. The excess THF was removed and dried under reduced pressure. The potassium phenoxide was again dissolved in benzene and to it a freshly distilled SbCl_3 (3.13 g, 13.71 mmol) solution in benzene (~ 20 ml) was added. The contents were refluxed for another 1 h. After cooling, KCl formed during the reaction was filtered out and the excess solvent was removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure. A yellow solid product in quantitative yield (80%) was obtained (Table 1).

Synthesis of $[\text{Sb}(\text{OAr})_3]$: Sodium (0.36 g, 1.57 mmol) was taken together with 2,4,6-trimethylphenol (2.02 g, 1.49 mmol) in THF (~ 30 ml). The contents were refluxed till sodium was completely dissolved and a clear and transparent solution was obtained. THF was then completely removed under reduced pressure to give a solid. It was again redissolved in benzene, and SbCl_3 (1.13 g, 0.49 mmol)